

Handbook for Educators
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S I U E

Artificial Intelligence (AI) in today's era

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The rapid development of Artificial Intelligence (AI) offers an excellent way to transform education. AI's ability to personalize the student learning experience and simplify administrative tasks will benefit both instructors and students.

This handbook aim to improve students engagement in class activities by detailing the valuable role of AI for instructors, staff, and teaching assistants of Southern Illinois University Edwardsville (SIUE). It will also serve as a guide to educate educational on the ethical and practical use of AI to bridge the gap in student engagement and Improve student productivity.

Purpose of the handbook

To help SIUE Instructors and Teaching assistants understand how the use of Artificial Intelligence models help in improving teaching and learning activities.

To provide instructors with practical tips on the use of Artificial Intelligence models in ways that can improve students learning.

To keep up with the changing needs of students in the digital age by offering easy-to-follow procedure and ethical guidelines for integrating Artificial Intelligence models in higher education

Objectives

- **Instructors' Awareness and Utilization.** While students rapidly adopt AI tools, many instructors remain uncertain about incorporating AI models into their teaching activities. In this regard, this manual is a guide for faculty members and TAs.
- To address ethical considerations of using AI in the educational setting.
- To improve student involvement and participation in class activities.

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SWOT ANALYSIS

Strength

- The handbook incorporates the perspectives of AI experts to provide valuable insights and guidance on the use of AI in educational settings.
- It helps instructors understand how AI models can help to personalize learning experiences, provide real-time feedback, and improve students' academic performance.

Opportunities:

- Incorporating AI into teaching activities can enable innovative teaching activities tailored to individual student's needs and learning styles.
- This handbook will help in decision-making for instructors by providing insights into student performance, learning patterns, and areas of improvement

Weakness

There are different opinions among AI experts regarding the best practice for integrating AI into educational settings, making it challenging to develop a unified approach.

To effectively make use of this model, it must be used ethically and responsibly, ensuring that biases are minimized, privacy is protected, and data is used securely.

Threat

Resistance to Change:

Some instructors may resist integrating AI into their teaching activities due to a lack of familiarity, fear of technology, or concerns about job security.

The Target Audience

The target audience for raising awareness of artificial intelligence (AI) in educational settings includes SIUE faculty members, educational policymakers, and teaching assistants.

1. **Faculty Members:** Faculty members are essential targets for AI awareness since they directly impact students' educational engagement. They will benefit from this project by understanding how AI can enhance teaching and learning processes, improve student engagement, and ease administrative tasks.

2. **Education Policymakers:** This handbook aims to educate educational policymakers since they shape the direction and policies of universities. Educating them about the benefits of AI in education can influence their decisions relating to funding, resource allocation, and curriculum development.

3. **Teaching Assistants:** Teaching assistants (TAs) often work closely with faculty members and students. They will benefit from this handbook by understanding how AI can support their roles, such as providing personalized feedback from students, assisting in grading, or offering additional learning resources that can help in improve Instructor-student communication. Educating TAs about AI models can empower them to effectively use these tools and enhance their teaching activities

How universities now implement Artificial intelligence into their policy

Duke
UNIVERSITY

Duke University, located in Durham, North Carolina, is a prestigious private research university known for its exceptional academic programs and strong emphasis on interdisciplinary cooperation.

What sets their approach apart from others?

- Grants are offered for instructors looking to improve their curriculum with Artificial Intelligence integration.
- Encourage instructors to implement AI in student assignments and offer guidance for its integration.
- Provide a general resource for AI usage to ensure all instructors are AI-literate.

Website to visit

<https://learninginnovation.duke.edu/ai-and-teaching-at-duke-2/artificial-intelligence-and-assignment-design/>

<https://learninginnovation.duke.edu/research-evaluation-development/ai-jump-start-grants/>

The University of Kansas, established in 1865, is a public research institution that actively participates in a wide array of teaching and research activities

What they are doing?

- Created center for teaching excellence AI Resources
- Created AI videos for instructors with limited experience in effectively utilizing AI models to improve teaching activities.
- Created a website on how instructor can best use these tools though extracting information from large language modules.

Link to the website

<https://cte.ku.edu/kucte-ai>

THE UNIVERSITY
OF ARIZONA®

The University of Arizona is a public research university known for its vital academic programs. Founded in 1885, the university offers various undergraduate, graduate, and professional degree programs across various fields of study

How are their actions distinct from the usual practices???

- Developed a clear and concise guide for instructors on the best methods for using ChatGPT.
- Create a simple learning program for instructors and students to increase their knowledge of AI.
- Arrange regular workshops and training sessions on AI literacy and teaching strategies.

Link to website

<https://libguides.library.arizona.edu/ai-literacy-instructors>

The University of California, Riverside (UCR), is a renowned public research university committed to excellence in education, research, and community engagement.

What sets their approach apart from others?

- Grant access to Google's generative AI platform using the school email covered by a contractual agreement.
- Provide a stepwise guide for instructors with the interest in incorporating AI into their teaching methods.

Link to the website

<https://teaching.ucr.edu/ai-classroom#understand-ai-potential>

Ayodeji Adeniyi
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New Mexico Highland
University

Usefulness of AI from Experts

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is a branch of computer science that aims to create machines capable of solving tasks that typically require human intelligence. This can be learning, problem-solving, perception, language understanding, and text generation, e.t.c

We are all thrilled these days by the mind-blowing capabilities of generative AIs like the Google Gemini, HuggingFace Chat, and OpenAI Chat-GPT which are examples of Large Language Models (LLMs).

Large Language Models (LLMs)

LLMs are AI models trained on vast amounts of text data to understand and generate human-like text. It is no longer limited to generating text alone, it can also generate images and perform language translation, and code generation, to mention a few.

An example of an LLM is the Open-AI Chat GPT which generates coherent and contextually relevant text based on the prompt given to it in the form of questions. It has been used to solve mathematical problems, write fiction stories, and answer trivia questions. Many people now heavily depend on ChatGPT rather than Google Search for whatever information they need. It is believed to save time and stress from navigating through each Google Search result.

Prompt Engineering

A prompt is a set of instructions or questions given to an LLM. A prompt can be as simple as “Hi” which the LLM would then reply to with some greetings and ask what it can help you with. Prompt engineering involves crafting improved and clear prompts to get the desired output from the LLM.

How ChatGPT can be a useful tool for an academic instructor:

Instructors can use Chat GPT to further break down course or subject modules into simpler forms. With a good prompt, instructors can use it to generate assessment questions from a class note, and can also use it to perform a quick evaluation of the student's performance.

How to use Chat GPT to generate assessment questions from class material:

To get the best output from the LLM, I will use a prompt engineering framework called COSTAR.

C stands for Context (Background information)

O for Object (Task)

S for Style (Writing pattern)

T for Tone (The expected tone)

A for Audience (Stating the targeted audience)

R for response (How you want the output formatted)

For example:

#CONTEXT#

I am a Biology instructor. I have a pdf file from one of the classes I took this semester. This particular PDF contains just a topic from several other topics I've taught this semester. It is almost finals week, and I need to set some exam questions for my students using this PDF.

#OBJECTIVE#

Using your maximum number of tokens, I want you to generate a summary of this topic, and at least five questions from it.

#STYLE#

The summary should be written in an informative style, and should not contain ambiguous words. It should be as simple as possible and should still explain what the document contains without giving false information. When you are about to run out of tokens, end the statement with "..."

#TONE#

Be positive in your response. Your output should not contain harmful words.

#AUDIENCE#

This output should target a sophomore student with Biology as their major. It is meant to be their semester final exam.

#RESPONSE#

Your output should start with the summary and then the question. That is, generate a detailed summary of this file, and then generate a set of five possible questions.

Steps:

- Open your internet browser and visit <https://www.chatgpt.com>
- In the text input field, you can type your prompt (the set of instructions you have for the AI) e.g "Hello"

- ChatGPT now supports attaching files, and you can ask the AI questions about the attached file. So I will be attaching a PDF from which I want ChatGPT to generate some exam questions and overview. (Click on the office pin icon to upload a file)

#####

 Connect to Google Drive

 Connect to Microsoft OneDrive >

 Upload from computer

student with Biology as their major. It is meant to be

your response should start with the summary and then the question. That is, generate a detailed summary of this file, and then generate a set of five possible questions.

ChatGPT can make mistakes. Check important info.

 Hi there! How can I assist you today?

 BIOL 233 - Female reproductive sys...
PDF

#CONTEXT#

I am a Biology instructor. I have a pdf file from one of the classes I took this semester. This particular PDF contains just a topic from several other topics I've taught this semester. It is almost finals week, and I need to set some exam questions for my students using this PDF.

#####

#OBJECTIVE#

Using your maximum number of tokens, I want you to generate a summary of this topic, and at least five questions from it.

Here is the ChatGPT response to my question after clicking the send icon or pressing the enter button..

ChatGPT

not contain ambiguous words. It should be as simple as possible and should still explain what the document contains without giving false information
When you are about to run out of tokens, end the statement with "..."
#####

#TONE#
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#####

#RESPONSE#
Your output should start with the summary and then the question.
That is, generate a detailed summary of this file, and then generate a set of five possible questions.

Summary

The female reproductive system includes various structures and processes essential for reproduction. The key components include:

1. **External Genitalia:** Protect the internal reproductive organs and facilitate sexual reproduction.
2. **Vagina:** A passageway for childbirth and menstrual discharge, with an acidic environment to prevent infections.
3. **Uterus:** A hollow, muscular structure supported by ligaments, consisting of three layers: perimetrium, ●

Message ChatGPT

ChatGPT can make mistakes. Check important info.

2. What are the phases of the ovarian cycle, and what key events occur in each phase?
 - **Answer:** The ovarian cycle has two main phases:
 - **Follicular Phase:** Occurs from days 1-14, involving the development of follicles in the ovaries.
 - **Luteal Phase:** Occurs from days 14-28, characterized by the formation of the corpus luteum from the remnants of the ovulated follicle, which secretes hormones necessary for maintaining the endometrium.
3. Explain the process of oogenesis and the stages it involves.
 - **Answer:** Oogenesis is the process of forming primary oocytes from oogonia. Primary oocytes are present at birth in the ovarian cortex and remain arrested in prophase of meiosis I until puberty. Upon puberty, about 250,000 primary oocytes survive, and approximately one oocyte completes meiosis I each month in response to luteinizing hormone (LH), then halts in meiosis II at metaphase, only completing meiosis II upon fertilization.
4. What changes occur in the female reproductive system during menopause, and what are some associated symptoms?
 - **Answer:** Menopause typically occurs between the ages of 46-54 and is marked by a significant decline in estrogen production. This leads to the atrophy of reproductive organs and breasts, decreased vaginal lubrication, irritability, depression, vasodilation and sweating (hot flashes), thinning of the skin, and loss of bone mass due to reduced calcium uptake.
5. How does the menstrual cycle prepare the female body for potential pregnancy, and what happens if fertilization does not occur?
 - **Answer:** The menstrual cycle prepares the body for pregnancy through several phases:

Message ChatGPT

ChatGPT can make mistakes. Check important info.

- Answer: Oogenesis is the process of forming primary oocytes from oogonia. Primary oocytes are present at birth in the ovarian cortex and remain arrested in prophase of meiosis I until puberty. Upon puberty, about 250,000 primary oocytes survive, and approximately one oocyte completes meiosis I each month in response to luteinizing hormone (LH), then halts in meiosis II at metaphase, only completing meiosis II upon fertilization.

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- Answer: Menopause typically occurs between the ages of 46-54 and is marked by a significant decline in estrogen production. This leads to the atrophy of reproductive organs and breasts, decreased vaginal lubrication, irritability, depression, vasodilation and sweating (hot flashes), thinning of the skin, and loss of bone mass due to reduced calcium uptake.

5. How does the menstrual cycle prepare the female body for potential pregnancy, and what happens if fertilization does not occur?

- Answer: The menstrual cycle prepares the body for pregnancy through several phases:
 - Proliferative Phase: The endometrium rebuilds itself.
 - Secretory Phase: The endometrium thickens and becomes more glandular in preparation for embryo implantation.
 - Premenstrual Phase: If fertilization does not occur, the corpus luteum degenerates, leading to the breakdown of the endometrium.
 - Menstrual Phase: The endometrial lining is shed, resulting in menstrual bleeding.

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Message ChatGPT

The Ethical Concern of LLM APPS

Since conversations with the OpenAI models are often used to further improve the performance of the AI, therefore, it is not advisable to paste or type sensitive data in it as this might be accessible by the platform.

Furthermore, ChatGPT or LLM are liable to make mistakes . It is then advisable to solely liable on its output even when it seems so true. You can always verify the truthfulness of its output when the output is to be used to make a crucial decision.

SIUE

2nd Speaker

Okonwo Dominick
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Artificial intelligence (AI) is a broad field that spans various disciplines such as computer science and philosophy. At its core, AI has the capability of a machine or computer program to perform tasks that typically require human intelligence. This includes learning from experience, recognizing patterns, understanding natural language, and making decisions. Simply put, AI refers to intelligence that originates from computers rather than humans. AI aims to generate responses close to human-level intelligence but sometimes has limitations.

For instance, if you ask human, "What is $1 + 1$?" the immediate response would be "2." Similarly, if you ask a computer the same question, it immediately responds with "2." However, if you then ask a human if there are other ways $1 + 1$ can yield a different answer, after a short period of thinking, you might get answers such as in binary arithmetic, $1 + 1$ equals "10," and in modulus arithmetic, $1 + 1$ equals "0 (mod 2)." If you ask an AI language model like ChatGPT the same question, it will provide a similar answer derived from its extensive data library.

One of the many answers you can get from human when you ask if $1 + 1$ is not equal to 2 might be, in marriage, $1 + 1$ equals 1. This is pure human reasoning. Then when a man and woman get married, they become one body, but a computer would not give you this unless it is explicitly trained to say so. This is just an example telling how human thinking and computer level thinking work

It Usefulness to Instructor and Students

Platforms like ChatGPT can help students better understand their teachers' instructions and teachings, facilitating learning. ChatGPT can simplify complex topics and even translate assignments into other languages. For example, you can ask ChatGPT to explain an assignment in simple English or clarify what the teacher wants you to do. ChatGPT and Perplexity can complement traditional teaching methods, recreate correspondence programs, and provide personalized study guides, thereby enhancing learning effectiveness. Additionally, these tools can aid both instructors and students in exam preparation.

Quillbot and Grammarly can help students restructure their sentences and correct grammar usage during writing and submissions, ensuring clear and concise language.

ChatGPT can help instructors grade student work and provide appropriate and well-defined feedback that students can understand and learn from. For instance, you can create a grading rubric or score bucket with categories such as 10 points, 7 points, 5 points, 3 points, 1 point, and zero points. Then, you can generate sample solutions for each of these points and give sample feedback (sample feedback is optional). Afterward, you can instruct ChatGPT to help you grade submissions from different students by assigning the appropriate points according to the score bucket and providing detailed feedback. You can copy and paste the submissions instead of sharing a document in this case. Google Gemini can do the same.

Gemini and ChatGPT can also help make notes more explanatory by integrating information from different documents. For example, if you want to create a note on the human body system using various documents, with one document discussing the circulatory system, another discussing the digestive system, and a third discussing the respiratory system, you can upload these documents to the platform. Then, you can instruct the software to create a well-written, long note about the body system that covers these three major systems. Your prompt should specify that paper one has information on the respiratory system, paper two on the digestive system, and paper three on the circulatory system. Additionally, you should explain how you want this output to be structured. Even if your prompt is long, as long as it is well-explained like you are talking to a human, the software will produce a detailed note.

Perplexity, ChatGPT, and Gemini can help explain difficult concepts to almost anyone. You can send a note or copy and paste a long, complex content and ask the AI to explain it in layman's terms, or at the level of a high school or lower grade student. The AI will do just that. You can also ask it to explain difficult concepts using everyday life analogies that anyone can understand. This can help instructors explain hard and new concepts to students. ChatGPT, and Gemini too, can explain code like a genius. Share your code with the AI and ask it to comment on every line of code. It will do this, and if you have difficulty understanding what a code does, the comments will help. If you need more detailed explanations about the code, you can then ask it to explain the code and what each part does after commenting, and it will do just that. This is super cool.

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Artificial Intelligence Today

If an instructor needs to create a note about something new and does not require referencing, they can use AI to create one. Tell it what you would like to achieve, then share your topic and ask for a good outline. After this, ask it to break down the outline into simpler subtopics. You can then work together with the AI to create notes on each subtopic and come up with something great.

QuillBot and Grammarly can help restructure your writing and correct grammar. Copy and paste your write-up or upload it, and let them help make corrections where necessary. ChatGPT can also help with grammatical errors and corrections like Quillbot and Grammarly do. Note that sometimes when you ask ChatGPT to make some edits to your work, such as a story, it may add some extras that were not in your initial input. Therefore, you need to explicitly tell it what to do and not assume it knows what you want. Here is an example of how you can do that: "Please help make this fluent, correct spelling and grammatical errors, and add the right punctuation. I have noticed it misses some conjunctions, and the flow from sentence to sentence is not as good, so I want you to help with that too. I also want it in very simple English. Do this without adding anything not in the content shared. It is storytelling, so try to stick to using past tense. Can you also help join the sentences to make it flow like a story?"

Please note that your effort in using all these tools is super important. You may not copy exactly what is output; you can make your corrections to their output.

Ethical consideration

Regarding AI like ChatGPT depends on various factors, with responsible usage being a major one. Instructors and students who sometimes use these software tools for writing and assignments may copy whatever output is given. However, because AI is limited, it may sometimes provide answers that are not entirely correct or may hallucinate which can be harmful in different ways. Instructors have an ethical obligation to ensure the accuracy of the information.

Also, not all data should be shared with AI, especially private data or information that may require student confidentiality. Protecting this data and ensuring it is used ethically and securely is important.

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How can instructors use these for their own advantage??

Instructors can use these tools to create better notes for their students something well centered on what the students are currently learning and their capacity to learn instead of a one-size-fits-all model. They can use these tools to create mock practice test/exam questions for students before their final exams and to provide additional explanations of concepts for students. Many of these AIs can help instructors create interactive lessons that include quizzes, polls, and multimedia content.

Recommendations

Based on what this project has created so far, I recommend SIUE do these things to integrate AI knowledge into the system.

- **Develop AI Center or Lab:** To make learning more engaging and interactive at SIUE, I recommend creating AI labs or centers where faculty and students can collaborate on AI research projects. This lab will explore new ways to make learning more engaging and improve communication between instructors and students. Drawing inspiration from the successful AI labs at the University of Kansas, our AI center can offer resources to help instructors incorporate AI into their courses. This may include practical tips, FAQ guides, and even AI-focused podcasts featuring AI experts discussing topics like large language models and the use of advanced AI tools like ChatGPT in their teaching. This method will make AI more accessible and beneficial for all members of the SIUE community.
- **Create AI Curriculum Modules:** SIUE can integrate AI curriculum modules into existing courses across all departments to ensure students are exposed to AI concepts and applications, regardless of their major.
- **Student Projects/Competitions and Grant Access:** Getting students involved in AI projects and competitions to put their skills to the test and gain practical experience is another way of integrating AI into the system. This process may include submitting AI project ideas, finding a faculty mentor, gaining access to necessary resources, and showcasing their projects in competitions. I recommend providing funding for each AI project to encourage and make it a meaningful opportunity for students to demonstrate their skills and creativity while also offering valuable learning experience